

A REVIEW OF THE APPLICATION OF PREFABRICATED STRUCTURES USING BUILDING INFORMATION MODELING

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Abstract

Prefabricated construction technique is a reusable mold or "form" that is prepared in a controlled environment, transported to the construction site, and erected. Standardized and intended for the stability, longevity, and structural integrity of the structure, prefab construction technology comprises a variety of prefabricated parts such as walls, beams, slabs, columns, stairs, landings, and certain unique features. On the other hand, Building Information Modeling (BIM) is becoming increasingly accepted for prefabricated construction because it enables efficient design, construction, and construction through the production and management of virtual models that combine physical characteristics and functional behavior. Architects, civil engineers, and constructors have long been interested in new techniques of building construction that enhance quality, save time and cost, and raise their productivity. BIM is a multidimensional model that simulates building geometry, spatial connections, geographic data, the amount and qualities of all building components, and their intelligent interconnection. This technology is a novel approach to the design, development, and administration of buildings, characterized by very high quality and coordination. As a result of advancements in digital architecture, prefabrication, and all types of optimization in the design of structures, building information modeling technologies are increasingly used in construction industry projects. Building information modeling may have a considerable influence on prefabricated construction for this reason. In addition, it is intended to install prefabricated construction components and find operational interferences by examining the building model. This article analyzes the benefits and drawbacks of prefab construction. It also evaluates the global construction industry's requirement for insurance.

Keywords: *building, construction, technology, bim, country*

1. INTRODUCTION

Owing to the specific implementation problems and obstacles encountered by the majority of building projects, it is essential to apply modern technology to handle these issues in order to impact the two essential factors of time and cost. Avoid being affected by factors that have a negative effect on the success or failure of a project. Recent advances have been made in the field of providing alternative methods and techniques (1). A accurate virtual model of a structure, known as a BIM, simulates a building project in a virtual environment using BIM technology. The creation of a computerized building information model (2). Each component's parametric components have its own detail ideas and include the necessary information, including architectural and structural concepts, how to create and price them, and the installation date. It is applied on the model and evaluated from the design phase until the conclusion of the project's operational lifetime (3). Figure 1 depicts a building designed using building information modeling. Figure number two shows the premade components.

Figure 1: designing using building information modeling (18)

Figure 2: manufactured components (19)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Building information modeling has been the topic of a considerable variety of research, each of which has concentrated on different aspects and applications of the field. Each research, using a distinct technique, has discovered the need to analyze the status or effectiveness of the technology, improve it, appreciate its benefits, and advance its future development and wider deployment. The analyzed studies are often divided into three categories. The first category consists of research that have examined the degree of acceptance of building information modeling, as well as the obstacles and problems associated with its implementation. The third area is dedicated to research conducted to develop a model for enhancing and better understanding technology. The second category comprises research examining the applications, benefits, and usefulness of information modeling technology construction (4).

In a separate study, they identified barriers to the deployment of building information modeling. Via a questionnaire, this research determined that construction industry professionals are disinterested in and unfamiliar with building information modeling. It also found that a lack of support and a lack of desire to promote it are the greatest impediments to its adoption among policymakers. Additional obstacles to the application of this technology in Iran include the paucity of training materials and a lack of knowledge and comprehension. Additional challenges to the adoption of this technology include reluctance to adapt present methods, costs, Internet speed, a lack of vital infrastructure, and ignorance of potential benefits (5).

In contrast, based on studies conducted to the end of 2015, the United States is well ahead of other countries in terms of the production of scholarly articles in the field of building information modeling. The Nordic countries also rank 59 in the worldwide production of scientific articles in this field. This topic is based on a chart that was posted in 2012 and investigated through 2015. The ranking of the countries and their rating remain still in force after the competition has concluded. Notably, the significant difference depicted in the following diagram can be attributed to a number of factors, including the use of different operating systems, a preference for new technologies, the presence of universities and other educational institutions, and particular trends in building information modeling and construction management (6). The amount of papers produced in developed countries is seen in chart 1.

Figure 3: Articles published in the field of building information modeling by countries until 2015 (6)

3. BUILDING INFORMATION MODELING

The engineering, architectural, and construction sectors have a misunderstanding of the software component of building data modeling, despite its significance. Instead, data modeling is seen as a valuable tool. The generation of building information, which provides information on the whole structure as well as full, unified documents in a database, is a new advance in the design and documentation procedures employed in the construction industry. As these data are parametric, they are all interconnected. Each alteration to a model component affects all aspects of the project. Modeling of building data includes both actual building data and two-dimensional building maps, which are unusual in maps made using CAD software. (7,8)

3.1. Advantages of using building information modeling

3.1.1. Time-related issues: About time, BIM often reduces the amount of time required to produce construction drawings.

3.1.2. 4D models: By using 4D models, the construction planning chain may be analyzed and shared with the rest of the project team. The building model's components should be arranged into groups depending on the stages of construction and linked to project planning activities.

3.1.3. Cost-related issues: A feature of BIM is that each component offers data on its length, width, and height, as well as any other information necessary for a quantitative project estimate.

3.1.4. Eliminating waste: The ability to rapidly develop alternative models, maintain information and coherence of the stated model (preventing interference), and provide

automatic reports all contribute to reliable data that is typically discarded and reconstructed. Reduces the time and effort required to get information.

3.1.5. Quality: With BIM's many capabilities, it is straightforward to give the opportunity for quality verification and to attain the ultimate goal of higher-quality buildings. (9)

3.2. Disadvantages of using building information modeling

3.2.1. Conventional working practices and low acceptance of contemporary technologies in construction projects, especially in third-world countries.

3.2.2. The requirement for employee and operator training in consulting, employer, and contracting organizations.

3.2.3 According to several firms, one of the obstacles to the broad use of building information modeling is that it merely refers to 3D design. (9)

4. BUILDING INFORMATION MODELING IN SPAIN

Directive 2014/24/UE of the European Union has been implemented in the Spanish construction industry. Taking effect from 2016, the Directive Permits Member States to encourage, use, and even compel the use of Building Information Modeling (BIM) in EU-funded construction projects. Building Information Modeling is applied by Spanish AEC specialists to demonstrate that BIM technologies are currently utilized solely throughout the design phase of residential constructions. There are not many instances in which this technique is applied in other types of projects or in the construction, operation, and maintenance stages. Nevertheless, experts estimate that it will take at least three to five years to completely use BIM in construction projects (10). Figure 4 shows building information modeling in Spain.

Particularly in the building and architectural industries, Building Information Modeling (BIM) is gaining popularity in Spain. In recent years, the Spanish government has supported the use of building information modeling (BIM) in public projects, which has helped increase awareness and promote its usage in the private sector as well. Many professional organisations, including the Spanish Association of Surveying and Mapping, the Spanish Association of Engineering and Architecture Firms, and the Spanish Association of Construction Companies, advocate the usage of BIM in Spain. These organizations offer training and assistance for professionals seeking to use BIM, as well as promote the advantages of BIM to clients and other stakeholders. There are also a rising number of BIM software vendors in Spain, such as CYPE and Tekla, as well as worldwide businesses like Autodesk and Trimble. These businesses provide a variety of BIM tools and solutions, including design and modeling software, project management and collaboration platforms, and more. The Spanish government has launched a variety of regulatory steps to encourage the use of BIM in public projects. For instance, from 2018, BIM has been compulsory for all public construction projects in Spain. In addition, the government has established a BIM

Commission to monitor the deployment of BIM across many industries and to encourage software tool standardization and interoperability. (23)

Figure 4: Building information modeling in Spain (20,22)

5. PREFABRICATED PARTS

Many prefabricated building components are often used in the construction of structures, therefore decreasing waste formation and its negative environmental impacts. Moreover, the examination into the possible use of prefabricated systems in construction projects indicates that non-standard building components and building foundations are better suited for conventional construction systems. For the construction of dry wall systems, concrete roofs, external coatings, and steel structural frames, prefabricated building components are also preferred. As many prefabricated building components are also load-bearing, it is important to consider upgrading lightweight prefabricated building components. According to data analysis, conventional construction methods have not delivered satisfactory results for the construction industry. Using prefab methods, however, may reduce construction waste by half. In this field, traditional and regular construction techniques will also be beneficial, and costs may be drastically reduced via the use of automated operations, recycled or recyclable materials, and industrial-style assembly of prefabricated building components. (11) Figure 5 depicts the prefabricated components of a house.

Figure 5: prefabricated parts (21)

5.1. Advantages of using prefabricated parts

Many researchers have highlighted the advantages of prefabrication. The top seven advantages of utilizing prefab for data collecting are as follows: Strong design in the early stages of design for better prefab use; better monitoring of the quality improvement of prefab products; reduction of overall construction costs; faster execution; improved environmental performance through waste reduction; integration of design and execution; and aesthetic aspects of the building. (12-13-14-15-16-17)

5.2. Disadvantages of using prefabricated parts

The disadvantages of prefabrication have also been taken into consideration. Ten of these disadvantages fall into the following categories: lack of adaptability to design changes, high initial cost, dearth of relevant research, time-consuming in the early stages of design, lack of consideration of the benefits of using common construction methods in the workshop, and limited space on the construction site. About the prefabricated component depot, the problems with sealing when connecting the prefabricated components, the incompetence of the contractors, the visual uniformity of the project, and the low demand for prefabricated construction components (12-13-14-15-16-17)

6. INTEGRATION OF BUILDING INFORMATION MODELING AND PREFABRICATION

Let's move on to the advantages of prefabricated and semi-prefabricated steel, concrete, and facility designs that particular BIM software may apply to accomplish building projects swiftly, effectively, and with high-quality outcomes. We will make and utilize them. Among the advantages of working in a controlled environment are: Work is performed in a controlled environment in which the construction procedure, workplace, and equipment are defined. As a result, the joinery stage project execution time may be reduced, and the prefabrication

capacity can be increased to the point where even all joinery layers can be fully executed. With the aid of this feature, the construction site will be safer and more organized, allowing for assembly-line work and the limited use of equipment such as ladders and lifts. Preventing delays caused by inclement weather: The manufacturing and building sites for prefabricated components are commonly covered and enclosed, making it easier to finish the job in any adverse weather, which is one of the elements contributing to the popularity of this construction style in the areas. It has become cold. Raising the pace of component assembly on site: While the construction and processing of concrete are sped up by the fabrication and production of components using contemporary technology, it may be claimed that more time may be saved in the assembly of parts at the installation site. Before the introduction of BIM and its associated software, prefabricated sections were coordinated and pieced together using CAD, which had limitations in imagining how to create these three-dimensional structures accurately. But, with the introduction of BIM and software. It is used similarly to Tekla Structures, which permits the configuration of manufacturing (carrying components), building designs, assembly, and even the CNC cutting program when the planned structure is of the steel variety. This process has changed significantly, and it can be claimed that it contributes a great deal of energy to the design and construction of these structures (6).

7. PREFABRICATION STAGES IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY BASED ON BIM

- Like with other kinds of buildings, the building's overall design is generated by the design team, who then submits it to the prefabrication specialists for preparation.
- The components of the building are then divided into parts that may be assembled and, of course, transported in accordance with traffic restrictions.
- The design unit is then responsible for making the final selection and supplying the appropriate equipment and materials for the instruments that have been changed into prefabricated shapes.
- The assembly line is used to produce prefabricated components in accordance with instructions that are often developed depending on the implementation schedule of the project.
- The program describes how components are packed, counted, and identified prior to transmission to the site.
- Installation of components on-site (6)

8. CONCLUSION

Building information modeling is one of the construction industry's most promising innovations. This technology permits the development of very precise digital models of one or more buildings, which aids in the design process. The combination of BIM and prefabrication provides contractors with a unique opportunity to comprehend the process prior to undertaking a project. Prefabrication covers the planning, production, and installation of equipment. To practice the implementation sequence (production and installation), select production locations, depots, towers, and elevators, manage the project site, and evaluate the effects of their decisions prior to beginning implementation, the entire executive team, including main contractors, subcontractors, and builders in each production and installation department, can utilize virtual simulation facilities of the construction process.

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